

BLOWOUT 1989

Cdr. Joseph E. Vorbach and Lt. John E. Crowley, Jr.

U.S. Coast Guard
Washington, D.C. 20590

ABSTRACT

This paper will review the events surrounding the blowout of IXTOC I, and consider the legal and environmental effects of a Law of the Sea (LOS) Treaty on a potential oil well blowout in 1989. The present LOS negotiating text contains articles which detail specific marine environmental protection responsibilities at the national and international level with respect to seabed exploration and exploitation. The authors believe that a LOS regime will provide the framework within which resource exploitation can be undertaken pursuant to a more uniform set of international rules and standards which will facilitate offshore development and significantly enhance global protection of the marine environment.

THE BLOWOUT OF IXTOC I

Editor Garry Ridgeway, writing in the June 1979 issue of Offshore Engineer, described the rapidly changing developments relating to the exploitation of the continental shelf off Mexico in the following terms:

"Like flies to a honey pot, the international offshore industry is attracted to Mexico. The turn of the year announcement by state oil company Petroleos Mexicanos that its country had 40 billion barrels of proven reserves, a fair proportion of which lies offshore in the Gulf of Mexico, has served to speed the adrenalin of job-hungry professionals. Well might they eye the Gulf with envy, for the pace and intensity of construction in the Bay of Campeche, and its future potential are exhilarating."

Indeed oil production in the Bay of Campeche is said to have more potential than the North Sea and this potential has attracted construction firms from Japan, West Germany, and the United States. The development of this vast potential has been overseen by Petroleos Mexicanos (PEMEX), the Mexican national oil corporation. On June 3, 1979, PEMEX had been drilling an exploratory well approximately 80 kilometers northwest of Ciudad del Carmen, in the Bay of Campeche, with a semi-submersible drilling rig, SEDCO

1. The opinions or assertions expressed herein are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Government, the Department of Transportation or the U.S. Coast Guard.

135. SEDCO 135 had been leased by bare-boat charter by Perforaciones Marinas de Golfo, S.A., of Mexico City (Permargo), and was registered by Southeastern Drilling Inc. of Texas and homeported in New Orleans, LA.

At about 3:30 am drilling in the exploratory well, known as IXTOC I, reached a reservoir where a pressure of 6,000 psi and the failure of a mud pumping system contributed to the blowout of the well. A massive amount of oil and natural gas was released. As the natural gas ignited, explosions ensued, and flames up to 50 feet high cast an orange hue over the Bay of Campeche. The crew of the rig was evacuated and most of SEDCO 135 was destroyed. What remained of the rig was pulled into shallow waters and later scuttled. Apparently a damaged blow-out preventer, along with a disconnected drilling riser, prevented PEMEX from finding an easy shutdown solution, and oil gushed into the southwestern Gulf of Mexico. On the bright side, PEMEX had discovered what was estimated to be a huge petroleum field, however, the excitement of this discovery was dampened by the realization that it might take months to cap the well.

POST-BLOWOUT EVENTS

The blowout began a saga in oil well capping and pollution response activities that was to continue to unfold for nearly ten months. Many of the world's experts were to visit the scene during the interim period, providing different evaluations, making different suggestions, and trying various capping and cleanup techniques. Over a dozen local and foreign companies participated in the initial response. Norwegian firms, which had responded to the North Sea Ekofisk Bravo platform blowout in 1977, were among the first to arrive at the IXTOC I site. Response activities ranged from collecting over a million bales of hay for cleanup, to technically oriented attempts to cap the well. The U.S. Coast Guard's National Oil Pollution Strike Force contributed to the containment and cleanup efforts made at the well site. Experts from the United Nations Environment Program visited the site and filed a report with the Government of Mexico. Yet despite the best efforts of all involved, IXTOC I continued to discharge oil, at varying rates, over that ten month period and has become the offshore industry's largest spill in history. The initial discharge rate was estimated to be 30,000 barrels a day. In nearly a dozen days, 15 million gallons of oil was estimated to have spilled in the Gulf. At this stage the resulting oil slick covered an area 12km wide and 128 km long and was moving northwest, although still

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nearly 900 km from U.S. waters. By mid-July the oil had impacted on the Mexican Shore in the form of sheen and mousse (gelatin formation of emulsified oil) and was still nearly 500 km from U.S. waters. In mid-August tarballs and pancaked formations reached the U.S. shore on Padre Island, Texas while the discharge rate was finally lowered to 10,000 barrels a day. Before the well was finally capped, the discharge rate had been lowered further in successive steps to 4,000, 2,000 and finally 400 barrels a day. PEMEX has estimated that 140 million gallons of oil were discharged into the Gulf during the IXTOC I blowout.

A quick application of the spot market price to this figure translates the spill into an economic loss of over 1 billion dollars just on the value of the oil. Other losses may be harder to calculate. The fishermen of Ciudad del Carmen, one of the largest shrimping centers in the world, were among the first to be concerned about the future impact. However, most all of the western Gulf coast was to be threatened before the spill was contained, raising concerns by a wide spectrum of coastal interest groups. PEMEX has claimed that the fishing industry experienced good catches during the spill and that there has been no apparent biological damage. However, the tourist industries of both Mexico and the U.S. suffered from a bad season due to the oil impact on the beaches.

Containment and cleanup costs generated further substantial expenses. As soon as the threat of harm to the U.S. was recognized, the United States requested and was given authorization from the Government of Mexico to conduct cleanup operations in Mexican waters North of 25 degrees North Latitude. U.S. efforts included: making overflights and taking surface samples to help determine the position, movement and extent of the oil spill; visits to the well site by experts; operating a skimming system at the site; staging oil barriers off sensitive harbors and beaches; and ensuring commercial cleanup of impacted U.S. coastal regions. With the exception of some direct contract work for the Government of Mexico, most of the cleanup expenses were paid from a fund established by section 311 of the Federal Water Pollution Control Act. Nearly \$8 million from the fund had been committed by March 23, 1980 when PEMEX announced that the well was capped.

SUMMARY OF PROBLEMS

Although the well is now capped and very little surface pollution remains evident, there nevertheless remain a number of unresolved problems. They include: continuing cleanup operations, as necessary; compiling an accurate account of the events that lead to the discharge; resolving legal claims for damages; devising improved construction and production standards and procedures for off shore wells; improving containment and cleanup techniques; and implementing a regional contingency plan. These problems are not peculiar to IXTOC I. They, generally, have been considered before under various scenarios. The Ekofisk platform blowout in the North Sea left many of the same problems unresolved. Although that region was fortunate not to have felt the impact of oil on its shorelines, the states in the region felt a renewed sense of the realization that they each could feel the drastic effects of a future blowout. This sense of urgency was present even though

the region had an agreement calling for cooperative efforts in case of an oil spill and had signed a convention establishing a regional liability regime.

The Gulf of Mexico region had no "Agreement" dealing with these issues when IXTOC I blew, however the incident is already proving to be a catalyst for contingency planning and efforts to develop a regional arrangement similar to that governing exploitation of the seabed of the North Sea might reasonably be expected. But what about all of the other regions where offshore exploitation is being conducted? Will successive regions face the same issues again and again and the process be repeated around the world?

BLOWOUT 1989

Let us now consider the legal and environmental effects that a Law of the Sea (LOS) Treaty would have on a future blowout and its aftereffects in 1989. The comprehensive provisions of the prospective LOS treaty should facilitate the development of legal regimes to deal with the problems encountered after IXTOC I. Wherever offshore mineral exploitation is undertaken, parties to the LOS treaty will be bound to a variety of obligations, all designed to protect and preserve the marine environment. Suppose that on June 3, 1989, potential oil well blowout (POWBO I) is being drilled in the Gulf of Mexico. The region has the same abundance of oil as was found at IXTOC I, is subject to the same weather conditions, is being used in connection with a diverse range of marine activities, and the protection of its environment will again be a concern to surrounding countries. Should a blowout occur, within what kind of regime will decision making be made and legal problems be sorted out?

THE LOS REGIME: BACKGROUND

In 1971, the UN Committee on Peaceful Uses of the Seabed and the Ocean Floor Beyond the Limits of National Jurisdiction divided itself into three subcommittees in preparation for the upcoming Third United Nations Conference on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS III). Subcommittee III was to "deal with the preservation of the marine environment (including, inter alia, the prevention of pollution) and scientific research...." Preservation of the marine environment embraced inter alia consideration of the sources of pollution and measures to combat them; measures to preserve the ecological balance of the marine environment; responsibility and liability for damage to the marine environment; rights and duties of coastal states; and international cooperation. In 1973 UNCLOS III began informal negotiations and in 1979 the chairman of the third committee reported that "the substantive negotiations on Part XII (Protection and Preservation of the Marine Environment)...could be considered as completed." ^{1/} The articles regarding the preservation of the marine environment should remain intact, with the exception of drafting changes, prior to incorporation in the final treaty. At this moment, it is possible that the conference could conclude all its work with the production of the long awaited LOS treaty in 1981.

Prior to the Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment (1972), the protection of the marine environment had been largely overlooked at the 1958 and

1960 conferences on the Law of the Sea. Committee III of the third LOS conference has for the first time addressed all sources of pollution including, inter alia, land based, vessel source, and pollution introduced as a consequence of seabed resource exploitation. States are required to take all necessary measures to prevent, reduce, and control pollution of the marine environment from any source, developing rules and standards appropriate to the different operations.

PART XII - PROTECTION AND PRESERVATION OF THE MARINE ENVIRONMENT

Protection and preservation of the marine environment are issues currently addressed in Part XII of the Informal Composite Negotiating Text/Revision 2, 2/ beginning, in Article 192, with a general obligation for all states "to protect and preserve the marine environment." The conference has expanded the details of this obligation in subsequent sections devoted to Global and Regional Cooperation; Technical Assistance; Monitoring and Environmental Assessment; International Rules and National Legislation to Prevent, Reduce and Control Pollution of the Marine Environment; Enforcement; Safeguards; Ice-Covered Areas; Responsibility and Liability; Sovereign Immunity; and, Obligations under Other Conventions on the Protection and Preservation of the Marine Environment. These sections further elaborate the obligations of parties to the treaty within the international, regional, and national communities, with respect to seabed exploitation.

RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS

Early in Part XII, Article 193 establishes the sovereign right of states "to exploit their natural resources pursuant to their environmental policies and in accordance with their duty to protect and preserve the marine environment." This right guarantees the continuation of offshore development and will ensure the feasibility, within the context of the treaty, of the drilling of our fictional POWBO I. Additionally, Part V (Article 56) recognizes that coastal states have sovereign rights to explore and exploit the resources of the Exclusive Economic Zones, while Part VI (Article 77) recognizes the same rights with respect to their continental shelves. (An acceptable formula for defining the outer limit of the continental shelf was finally devised during the recently concluded ninth session of UNCLOS III).

These rights are qualified by certain obligations in addition to the general obligation of Article 192. Article 194 is entitled "Measures to prevent, reduce and control pollution of the marine environment;" and reads, in part:

1. States shall take all necessary measures consistent with this Convention to prevent, reduce and control pollution of the marine environment from any source using for this purpose the best practicable means at their disposal and in accordance with their capabilities, individually or jointly as appropriate, and they shall endeavor to harmonize their policies in this connection.
2. States shall take all necessary measures to ensure that activities under their jurisdiction or control are so conducted that they do not cause

damage by pollution to other States and their environment, and that pollution arising from incidents or activities under their jurisdiction or control does not spread beyond the areas where they exercise sovereign rights in accordance with this Convention.

3. The measures taken pursuant to this Part shall deal with all sources of pollution of the marine environment. These measures shall include, inter alia, those designed to minimize to the fullest possible extent:...

(c) Pollution from installations and devices used in exploration or exploitation of the natural resources of the seabed and subsoil, in particular for preventing accidents and dealing with emergencies, ensuring the safety of operations at sea, and regulating the design, construction, equipment, operation and manning of such installations or devices;....

4. In taking measures to prevent, reduce or control pollution of the marine environment, States shall refrain from unjustifiable interference with activities in pursuance of the rights and duties of other States exercised in conformity with this Convention.

5. The measures taken in accordance with this Part shall include those necessary to protect and preserve rare or fragile ecosystems as well as the habitat of depleted, threatened or endangered species and other marine life.

Article 195 further specifies that all measures must be taken so as not to transfer damage from one area to another or transform one type of pollution into another.

INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS AND NATIONAL LEGISLATION

Thus far we have considered how the LOS treaty obligates states to prevent, reduce and control pollution of the marine environment. States will translate such requirements from international agreements imposed upon themselves into appropriate national standards under which offshore operators must work. Article 208 requires the establishment of international rules and national legislation to prevent, reduce and control pollution of the marine environment from seabed activities in the following ways.

1. Coastal States shall adopt laws and regulations to prevent, reduce and control pollution of the marine environment arising from or in connection with seabed activities subject to their jurisdiction and from artificial islands, installations and structures under their jurisdiction, pursuant to articles 60 and 80.
2. States shall also take other measures as may be necessary to prevent, reduce and control such pollution.

3. Such laws, regulations and measures shall be no less effective than international rules, standards and recommended practices and procedures.

4. States shall endeavour to harmonize their national policies at the appropriate regional level.

5. States, acting especially through competent international organizations or diplomatic conference, shall establish global and regional rules, standards and recommended practices and procedures to prevent, reduce and control pollution of the marine environment arising from or in connection with seabed activities subject to their jurisdiction and from artificial islands, installations and structures under their jurisdiction referred to in paragraph 1. Such rules, standards and recommended practices and procedures shall be reexamined from time to time as necessary.

Certainly, PEMEX had recognized its right to exploit the seabed when IXTOC I was drilled, but drafters of the LOS treaty intend to make all states who subsequently conduct offshore activities, such as POWBO I, equally aware of those measures that are expected to be employed in protecting the marine environment. The delegations of Mexico, Canada and the U.S. played key roles in negotiating the provisions of Part XII and these countries may be expected to take their environmental responsibilities quite seriously. The operators of POWBO I can expect to be required to conduct environmental assessments whenever there are reasonable grounds to expect that their activities may cause substantial pollution of or significant and harmful changes to, the marine environment. Furthermore, they will have to meet new standards of operation and take steps to prevent trans-border effects of pollution, once states have established adequate standards that will prevent, reduce and control pollution as required by Article 208. In furtherance of these obligations, states will monitor and assess the risks and effects of pollution and then publish them for the information of all states as required by Articles 204 and 205.

These requirements will not be burdensome for U.S. companies long accustomed to environmental impact statements and high safety and environmental standards. Rather, the LOS provisions will extend the application of such measures to the global community. It should be particularly noted that once international standards are developed, Article 208(3) obligates states parties to enact national laws and regulations that shall be no less effective than international rules, standards and recommended practices and procedures. There are, of course, no internationally accepted standards, nor a recognized competent organization to set them, however, Article 208(5) calls for the elaboration of standards to prevent marine pollution arising out of seabed activities. This could be accomplished through a diplomatic conference or competent international organization. An international organization competent in offshore industrial technology could be similar to the Intergovernmental Maritime Consultative Organization, IMCO. IMCO is the United Nation's body recognized as the competent international organization in technical and related matters affecting international shipping. The United Nation's Environment Program (UNEP) is the

U.N. body established to promote international cooperation and recommend policies in the field of the environment. UNEP has called for a worldwide conference in 1981 to further the development of international environmental law. With respect to seabed exploitation, it is hoped that the Conference will consider and move beyond the UNEP study of offshore mining and drilling within the limits of national jurisdiction and the subsidiary working papers relating to safety measures and contingency planning. However, it would facilitate the orderly development of offshore technology, as well as the exploitation of resources, if a specialized body with technical competence is created to deal with the unique problems associated with offshore exploration and exploitation. The U.S. delegation to a world conference called by UNEP should use the opportunity to recommend the establishment of a specialized agency for offshore technology.

A competent international organization dealing with the unique safety and environmental concerns of the offshore industry could be used as a sounding board where rapidly changing developments and improvements can be coordinated. Following the capsizing of the Alexander L. Kielland in the North Sea on March 27, 1980, questions have been raised concerning the adequacy of standards for similar rigs. The repercussions may be felt in the Gulf of Mexico and are likely to impact on the Norwegian decision to exploit north of the 62nd parallel. In a world that is politically and economically volatile, especially with respect to the offshore industry, international agreement on technical standards may provide the stabilizing influence that will allow a POWBO I to be constructed in 1989. Clearly, global standards would provide predictability and stability for an industry whose interests are found the world over. Of course all regimes require enforcement and Article 214 of the LOS text provides that states shall "enforce their laws and regulations adopted in accordance with Article 208 and shall adopt the necessary legislative, administrative, and other measures" to implement these rules and standards.

GLOBAL AND REGIONAL COOPERATION

The drafters of the LOS text recognized the value of regional and international cooperation in meeting the requirements of Article 208. However, the treaty is more explicit in the requirement for cooperation in Articles 197-201. Article 197 calls for global and regional cooperation and requires that characteristic regional features be taken into account when elaborating international standards for the protection and preservation of the marine environment; Article 198 calls for the immediate notification of adjacent states when an incident threatens to damage the marine environment of the adjacent states; Article 199 promotes the use of contingency plans for responding to pollution incidents; Article 200 promotes scientific research and the exchange of information and data acquired about marine pollution; and Article 201 requires that the results of information obtained by virtue of Article 200 be used to elaborate standards developed to protect the marine environment.

CONTINGENCY PLANNING

Quite obviously the LOS Conference has placed a great

deal of emphasis on cooperation through all stages of the process undertaken for the protection of the marine environment. Article 198 will require cooperation in the critical early stages of an international spill when appropriate preparations for responses must be taken to be most effective. While cooperation between Mexico and the U.S. was evident in the response to IXTOC I, the contingency plan referred to in Article 199 has only since been pushed towards completion in an effort to have it ready for any future incident.

The Baltic, The North Sea, and U.S.-Canadian waters have all been covered by agreements ^{3/} setting forth policy and requirements for contingency planning. While each is different in scope, depending upon regional circumstances, they provide an insight to what is envisioned by Article 199 of the LOS text. The Baltic states formed a joint commission to act as overseer for planning and response. Specific responsibilities include: implementation of the Convention; definitions of objectives; and the promotion of cooperation in disseminating information and conducting research. The Bonn Agreement for cooperation in the North Sea establishes regions of responsibility for each state and ensures that the national agency responsible for pollution protection in each region is prepared to assist other states. The U.S.-Canadian Agreement directs the U.S. Coast Guard and Canadian Ministry of Transport to administer a contingency plan. Each of these plans provides for activation of prearranged response and communications mechanisms and will no doubt serve as models for future contingency planning. By 1989 plans similar to these should facilitate rapid and effective application of resources to contain, control and cleanup in the aftermath of any blowout.

RESPONSIBILITY AND LIABILITY

Damages are what international standards, national legislation, and cooperative efforts are supposed to prevent or minimize. Nevertheless, the best human efforts bear a risk of failure, hence Article 235 of the LOS text provides as follows:

1. States are responsible for the fulfillment of their international obligations concerning the protection and preservation of the marine environment. They shall be liable in accordance with international law.
2. States shall ensure that recourse is available in accordance with their legal systems for prompt and adequate compensation or other relief in respect of damage caused by pollution of the marine environment by natural or juridical persons under their jurisdiction.
3. With the objective of assuring prompt and adequate compensation in respect of all damage caused by pollution of the marine environment, States shall cooperate in the implementation of existing international law and the further development of international law relating to responsibility and liability for the assessment of and compensation for damage and the settlement of related disputes, as well as, where appropriate, development of criteria and procedures for payment of adequate compensation such as

compulsory insurance or compensation funds.

In the calculation of damages, the injured party wants prompt compensation for what he considers to be undesirable effects suffered as a consequence of an incident. On the other hand, the party responsible for an incident wants to be protected against unacceptable financial loss. This is particularly true for the offshore industry which undertakes a risk of financial loss in the mere drilling of a well. The resolution of these needs is frequently difficult and can wreak havoc on the principals to the dispute. Parties to the IXTOC I case are finding the dispute settlement process unprepared to handle the problem. While the Texas tourist industry, the Gulf of Mexico fishermen, and the Texas Attorney General have claimed damages of about \$365 million, SEDCO has sought to limit its liability and Mexico has refused to recognize any claims not filed in Mexican courts. This is the kind of problem, that left unresolved, delays payment to injured parties and ties up personnel and resources of industry and government. Article 235 will ease this burden in two ways. First, it requires that each state assume responsibility to ensure that a recourse is available to injured parties for compensation of damages. Secondly, this article calls upon states to join together in regional and global agreements to aid in the development of international law with respect to liability for damages and to formulate adequate plans for compulsory insurance or compensation funds.

The offshore industry demonstrated an understanding of these concepts in 1973 when delegates from nine Northwest European states met to devise the Offshore Pollution Liability Agreement (OPOL). ^{4/} Operators were required to establish financial responsibility up to \$50 million per year in return for a limitation of liability at \$25 million per incident. In return for the limit on liability, operators are strictly liable without proof of fault and the agreement further provides that the operators are the exclusive source of compensation for damages, although the operators still are able to seek recovery from third parties under various national liability laws. Injured parties are assured of at least some compensation, while the industry's risk of financial loss is lessened.

The governments followed in 1976 with a Convention on Civil Liability for Oil Pollution Damage Resulting from Exploration for and Exploitation of Seabed Mineral Resources. ^{5/} The Convention was a compromise, reflecting different national liability schemes, that will provide one scheme of compensation for North Sea states. States are given the opportunity to allow higher limitations or unlimited liability as opposed to the amount agreed to in the convention, but injured parties from all states are assured of minimum compensation. This Convention becomes the exclusive remedy for all parties.

This example shows the value of state cooperation in the formulation of a liability and compensation regime. With a similar regime for the Gulf of Mexico in 1989, claimants would not be faced with expensive litigation as a prelude to an uncertain recovery, while the operators of POWBO I would know long before drilling is commenced what their liability exposure will be.

DISPUTE SETTLEMENT

To insure adherence to the provisions of a LOS treaty by the eventual parties, the present negotiating text contains extensive provisions for the compulsory settlement of disputes. These provisions underscore the obligations of the parties and will serve as a prod to the fulfillment of the duties relating to seabed exploitation described above.

CONCLUSION

As the foregoing illustrates, a LOS regime will provide the framework within which resource exploitation can be undertaken pursuant to a more uniform set of international rules and standards designed to protect and preserve the marine environment. Assuming the remaining obstacles to a LOS agreement can be resolved so as to permit the signing of an agreement in 1981, and the parties to that agreement act promptly to cause the treaty to enter into force by 1985, by 1989, the international community may be expected to have developed a set of uniform standards for the construction, operation, and manning of offshore facilities in an attempt to prevent the pollution of the marine environment. Industry can benefit from a regulatory environment that is predictable, yet flexible enough to accommodate ever changing technology. The environment on the other hand will benefit from a regime that can administer generous ounces of prevention as well as a pound of cure, while individuals will find a legal regime more conducive to successfully resolving questions of liability for damages.

Under a LOS regime in 1989 the operators of POWBO I will hopefully be better able to deal with the variety of problems encountered in connection with the IXTOC I

blowout which were discussed at the outset of this paper.

Regional and global cooperation will permit interested states to discuss problems, make contingency plans and act in concert. Response efforts will be thought out and provide access to all available assistance. Industry and national response teams will be able to react immediately through established channels to commence actions after a POWBO I blowout.

Finally, industry and other users of the oceans will find a more reliable mechanism to resolve liability and compensation issues. Industry will know the extent of its liability while the potential victims of an oil spill such as the fishing and tourist industries of the Gulf will be assured of prompt compensation for proven damages.

All users of the oceans should find themselves in a more acceptable regime - from construction, to cleanup, to payment of damages - by virtue of the provisions of a prospective LOS treaty and the prime beneficiary of these endeavors will be the environment we inherited and pass on to succeeding generations.

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